

CHALLENGES OF IT TERMINOLOGY TRANSLATION FROM ENGLISH INTO ROMANIAN BASED ON THE CLARIN PARALLEL CORPUS

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The growing internationalization of IT underscores the urgent need for accurate and consistent translation of IT terminology from English into Romanian. This study focuses especially on data from the Romanian–English parallel corpus developed within the CLARIN infrastructure. The research categorizes translation techniques into direct and indirect methods and assesses their frequency and effectiveness based on corpus data. A subcorpus of 5,000 aligned IT term pairs was compiled and analyzed to determine the distribution of methods such as calque, borrowing, transposition, modulation, and equivalence. The results show that calque (42%) and borrowing (25%) are the most common methods for transferring IT terminology into Romanian, while transposition (8%), modulation (5%), and equivalence (3–4%) ensure idiomatic accuracy and functional clarity. The study demonstrates how bilingual corpora, particularly those from CLARIN, can support empirical research in technical translation.